

EMPLOYABILITY OF TOURISM GRADUATES: A CASE STUDY OF HANOI UNIVERSITY, VIET NAM

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

The global tourism and travel industry generated 334 million jobs in 2019, accounting for one-fourth of all new jobs worldwide (WTTC, 2021). However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the industry's contribution to the total travel and tourism GDP decreased from 10.4% to 5.5% (ILO, 2020). Vietnam is one of the top 10 places where tourism is growing fastest in the world, with more than 18.008 million international tourists and 85 million domestic tourists coming to the country. As of December 2019, there were 2,648 international travel agencies with 26,864 tour guides and 30,000 accommodation establishments with 650,000 rooms in the country (Hanh, 2021). The demand for human resources in the industry continues to grow, but the supply of qualified workers has not kept pace. To ensure the industry's sustainability and growth, there is a need to retrain current workers and prepare new graduates to fill the skills gap. The focus of the DBA study is on the professionalism and employability of tourism graduates, which are key concepts that will help bridge the gap between the industry's demand for skilled workers and the higher education system's ability to produce them.

Understanding and perception of graduate employability is still inconsistent, especially for tourism graduates, who are not prepared to meet requirements of employers. Higher education institutions (HEIs) still consider consumers' views on their employability development strategy. A more general understanding of employability, including the perspectives of tourism graduates, has received little research interest (McQuaid & Lindsay, 2005; Eldeen et al., 2018; Eurico et al., 2015). The study examines the perspectives of the tourism industry, HEIs, and students, focusing on graduate employability and professionalism of tourism graduates as shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 2. Three Perspectives: Graduates, University and Tourism Industry

The study is focusing on the Vietnam tourism industry, where concepts such as employability and professionalism play a central role, and the organization with which the author is presently working, namely the Hanoi University.

LITERATURE REVIEW

EMPLOYABILITY

The employability of tourism graduates has been influenced by several factors, including educational background, professional competencies, workplace environment, and necessity. Recent studies have shown that soft skills are often seen as more important than hard skills for getting a job and being successful (Chen et al., 2021; Dhaliwal & Misra, 2020). Williams et al. (2019) give a full explanation of employability based on eight factors, including human capital, social capital, cultural capital, psychological capital, adaptability, mobility capital, self-management, and signaling. Recent studies have demonstrated that employability is not just determined by a person's capacity to function and retain steady work but also by the presence of appealing personal attributes that enhance their employment chances (Chen et al., 2021; Dhaliwal & Misra, 2020). In reality, soft skills are frequently more important than hard talents when it comes to finding work and establishing success (Guilbert et al., 2016). Typically, recruiters prefer applicants with both the technical skills and interpersonal traits essential to overcome external challenges (Sato et al., 2021). This emphasis on interpersonal skills is especially pertinent in the "people business" sector, where soft talents may be prioritized above hard abilities (Sato et al., 2021).

Studies on the job prospects of Vietnamese college graduates have come up with interesting results and ideas for more research. Tran et al. (2022) suggest a curriculum reform and career counseling that emphasizes generic professional skills and contextualized traits like adaptability, flexibility, resiliency, dedication, and continual learning. Lan (2018) found a significant gap between academic knowledge and skills and the nature of employment. Le, H.N.T. (2018) identifies a skills gap among graduates of higher education in Vietnam. Graduates lack the abilities essential to do their professions successfully, particularly soft skills such as communication, managerial and supervisory skills, teamwork and problem-solving, leadership, and project management. The lack of skills is attributable to tertiary education institutions' inability to grasp the demand for skills in the job market, poor teaching capacity, student disengagement, limited resources, and a lack of support from external stakeholders. Cooperation, adaptability, active listening, risk-taking, public speaking skills, and critical thinking are found to contribute more effectively to employability than other skills (Le Thai Hung & Pham Thi Anh Phuong, 2019). In line with the three-perspective approach, this DBA study will derive and deploy a definition as follows:

Graduate employability is a set of professional (Epstein et al., 2002, p.226; Nadia et al., 2019) and personal (Teijeiro et al., 2013; Zehrer & Mössenlechner, 2009) competences, employability (Donida & Lapina, 2020) and soft (Nilsson, 2010; Tsirkas et al, 2020) skills that are developed and learned in HEIs to prepare graduates to get the job and excel in their workplace (Abd Samad et al., 2018; Sato, 2021).

PROFESSIONALISM

Studies have linked employability with competencies (Epstein, R.M. et al, 2002 Fergusson et al., 2020; Widayati, A., 2017), and current research on Vietnamese Universities suggests this is true (Thuan, P.V., et al., 2019; Duc, P.H., 2021; Tran, L.T., et al., 2022; Hanh, N.D, Loan, V.Q., Viet, N.M, 2020; Lan, M.T.Q., 2018; Le Huu Nghia Tran, 2018; Hung, L.T. & Phuong, P.T.A., 2019). Flexner's (1915) six criteria for professions are that they involve intellectual operations with large individual responsibility, derive their raw material from science and learning, possess an educationally communicable technique, tend to self-organization, and are becoming increasingly altruistic in motivation. Professionalism is defined as the habitual and judicious use of communication, knowledge, technical skills, clinical reasoning, emotions, values, and reflection in daily practice for the benefit of the individual and community being served (Epstein, R.M. et al, 2002, p. 226).

Competencies referred to practical knowledge and skills assisting people to handle their tasks effectively (Nadia et al., 2019). Besides, competencies served as a standard of required KSAOs for employees to be successful at their workplaces (Abd Samad et al., 2018). Competencies can be identified more extensively, including individuals' KSAOs, collaborative teams, operation, and the company's capabilities to maintain competitiveness (Athey & Orth, 1999). Furthermore, qualifications are regarded as an advantageous source of competencies for prospective employees as well (Liu et al., 2021).

To support employees in maintaining their jobs in the industry, this study considers KSAOs as principal competencies for prospective employees. Competencies can help tourism graduates to orient the skills, knowledge, and content necessary for their work, improve service quality in this industry, and have the ability to face difficulties, challenges, and unexpected situations so as not to be passive and ready in their future jobs. Taking into account that professional competence is a part of the concept of "graduate employability," this DBA study will come up with and use the following definition:

“Professional competence is the practical knowledge (Nadia et al., 2019), generic and soft (Belchior-Rocha, H., Casquilho-Martins, I., & Simões, E., 2022) skills that employers expect from HEI's graduates (Donida & Lapina, 2020)”.

PERSONAL COMPETENCIES

Competencies are practical knowledge and skills that help people to handle their tasks effectively. They are a standard of required KSAOs for employees to be successful at their workplaces (Nadia et al., 2019; Abd Samad et al., 2018). Personal competencies are also a factor enhancing employability, with a relationship between competencies and employee performance being remarkable. This antecedent is considered a significant element to measure the employability of graduates (Teijeiro et al., 2013). Workers with competencies have more advantages to maintain and develop in a company (Dhaliwal & Misra, 2020; Abbas, 2021).

The demonstration of career adaptability will aid students in preparing themselves before entering the labor market and in being more adaptable in the face of unpredictable situations. Primarily, the research emphasizes the need for training programs for tourism students to adapt to their working environment. It also suggests that HEIs should adjust their training curricula and approaches to the varying needs of recruiters. Knowledge competencies can help tourism graduates improve their employability by helping them to orient the skills, knowledge, and content necessary for their work (Shyju, 2018). Since personal competence is another part of the concept of graduate employability, this DBA study will come up with and use the following definition:

Personal competence is the personal self-concept of their major strengths (Pool & Sewell, 2007; Kustyarini, 2020; Schreuder & Coetzee, 2016; Zehrer & Mössenlechner, 2009) and professional educational background (Sato, 2021) that are characterized by positiveness, friendliness, creativity, trustworthiness, integrity, flexibility, and dynamism (Sharif, 2014; Archer & Davison, 2008; McMurray et al., 2016; Park et al., 2016; Giang T., 2021). Emphasize that graduates need to have both personal attributes and HEI's education in this definition.

HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND INFORMAL LEARNING

University studies is the formal education and training offered to students at the tertiary level, often in a university or college. It focuses on subject-specific information, transferable skills, and chances for personal and professional growth in preparation for their chosen career path (Belchior-Rocha, H. et al., 2022; Schettino, G., Marino, L., & Capone, V., 2022).

In contrast, Andreina Bruno and Giuseppina Dell'Aversana (2018) examine the notion of a reflective practicum in higher education which encourages students to enhance their reflexivity and reflect on their experiences in order to acquire new knowledge. Schon's (1987) theory of reflective practicum states that the primary facilitators of reflective practicum are the use of groups and the role of instructors as trainers. Ryan, Mary, and Michael Ryan (2011) have incorporated and altered Schon's theory into a two-dimensional model for reflective learning and evaluation in higher education.

For Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), graduates' employability is critical and should be integrated into their intra-, co-, and extracurricular activities. HEIs must understand the demands placed on students who study full-time while also working part-time, recognize the benefits of obtaining hands-on experience, coordinate with business partners, source opportunities for possible employment, and give students proper support and guidance when needed (Zehrer & Mossenlechner, 2009). Non-formal education and non-formal learning have been at the center of discussions about lifelong learning (Hawley et al., 2010; OECD, 2010; Souto-Otero et al., 2005). Informal learning is unstructured, experiential, non-institutional, and non-curriculum-based learning that takes place during the course of ordinary work duties. A 3-P framework was used to investigate the diversity and interdependencies between various learning components (Hawley et al., 2010; OECD, 2010; Souto-Otero et al., 2005). Experiential learning (EXL) is a partial process of general learning that helps students to link academic learning with practical working knowledge in a specific industry.

Experiential learning is an important strategy for higher education, as it promotes learning satisfaction and equips students with essential job-related skills. Mentoring involves learning from someone who has more experience or expertise in a particular area, providing guidance and support, sharing knowledge and insights, and offering feedback to help learners improve their skills. Self-directed learning involves personal exploration and discovery, peer learning involves learning from others, informal social learning involves social interactions, abroad and domestic study programs provide students with the opportunity to study in a foreign country or visit a domestic location, and undergraduate research involves working on a research project with a faculty member or research team (Kong & Yan, 2014; Cronin & Lowes, 2016; Yang et al., 2015; Nenzhelele, 2014).

THE INDUSTRY AND WORK INTEGRATED LEARNING

Work integrated learning (WIL) is a combination of knowledge and skills obtained at on-campus and off-campus. It has been found to have a competitive advantage over others in terms of gaining future work in the hotel industry. WIL brings the opportunities for students to develop life skills such as communication, confidence and self-esteem (Martin et al., 2010). In Vietnam, work-integrated learning is still not in a complete performance due to the lack of cooperation between companies and universities. Reflection is an important factor that has an impact on work-integrated learning (Khuong, 2016).

WIL is an important part of preparing students for a career by giving them the chance to build relevant professional skills and apply and integrate academic knowledge with practical experiences (Coll & Eames, 2009; Jackson, 2006). There are several forms of WIL that institutions and employers can use to help students develop the skills and knowledge needed to succeed in the workforce: co-operative education, internships and placements, service learning, apprenticeships, simulations and case studies. These activities can provide students with an opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge to practical situations and develop problem-solving skills.

TOURISM GRADUATES' PERSPECTIVE

Zehrer and Mössenlechner (2009), found that personal attributes of individuals are appreciated in the tourism industry, and that being aware of one's own strengths is one of the most important characteristics of personal competencies. According to Sharif (2014), positiveness has a great influence on the employability of tourism students, as it is the motivation and belief to work enthusiastically. Creativity is also highlighted as an important item of these constructs, helping employees to solve work better, faster and more accurately. Lastly, friendliness is

an important item in personal attributes, which contributes to the success of employability (Charles, n/d). Friendliness is an important factor in a professional working environment in the tourism industry, while trustworthiness, integrity, flexibility, and dynamism are also important attributes employers look for in graduates (Archer & Davison, 2008; McMurray et al., 2016; Park et al., 2016; Giang T., 2021). However, there is an uprising issue of graduate unemployment due to skill gaps between the tourism industry and educational background (Wakelin-Theron et al., 2018; Tran Thi Hien et al., 2020).

RESEARCH GAPS, FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS AND RE-SEARCH QUESTIONS

Major research gaps and future research directions have been identified in recent studies on employability and its determinants. Williams et al. (2019) suggest that future research should focus on developing a comprehensive employability framework that considers both job-specific and transferable skills. Benbow and Hora (2018) suggest that future research should undertake field research methods on occupation- and discipline-specific views of valuable skills to explore how cultural models shape different competencies and their transfer into employment fields. Further research is recommended to explore the influence of external factors on employability such as industry trends and economic conditions and how HEIs can prepare students for a successful career without compromising the quality of academic courses (Cheng et al., 2022; Sato et al., 2021). Future research should look into educational background, training programs, and how job, relational and organisational characteristics affect informal learning in small businesses. Strategies to increase the beneficial effects of informal learning should be explored by examining case studies of successful cooperation between employers and universities (Coetzer et al., 2017). Taking into consideration the above mentioned research gaps and future research directions identified in current studies, this DBA study will aim at address the following research questions:

1. How can a comprehensive employability framework that considers both professional and personal competences be developed to enhance employability for tourism and hospitality graduates in Viet Nam?
2. What are the strategies for increasing the beneficial effects of informal learning in the tourism bachelor program of Hanoi University, and how can tourism industry and Hanoi University work together to enhance the effectiveness of their informal learning activities?
3. How can Hanoi University modify their training courses and methods to accommodate the diverse demands of recruiters and assist tourism students in adapting to the workplace and developing adaptive abilities?

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

RESEARCH APPROACHES AND METHODS

Based on Creswell and Poth (2018), the following research strategies are proposed for addressing the aforementioned three research questions:

To resolve the first research question, **narrative inquiry** may be an appropriate approach. This strategy emphasizes the narratives and experiences of individuals, enabling them to share their perspectives and experiences regarding employability in the tourism and hospitality industries. In addition to document analysis, data can be collected through interviews with graduates, employers, and other stakeholders. The data can then be thematically analyzed to determine the competencies necessary for employability in the industry and to develop a framework that takes into account both professional and personal competencies.

The second research question seeks to investigate strategies for enhancing the positive effects of informal learning in the bachelor's program in tourism at Hanoi University, as well as how the tourism industry and university can collaborate to increase the effectiveness of informal learning activities. **A case study** approach can be suitable to investigate this question because it permits an in-depth examination of a specific context and its complexities. Through interviews, observations, and document analysis, the researcher can collect data. The data can then be thematically analyzed to determine the effective strategies for enhancing informal learning as well as the factors that facilitate or impede its implementation.

The third research question seeks to determine how Hanoi University can modify its training courses and methods to meet the diverse needs of recruiters and assist tourism students in adapting to the workplace and developing adaptive skills. **Action research** is a suitable method for addressing this question because it entails collaboration between the researcher and the participants in identifying problems and developing solutions. The researcher can collaborate closely with faculty, students, and employers to determine the obstacles and opportunities associated with modifying training courses and methods. Focus groups, interviews, and observations can be utilized to acquire the data. The data can then be thematically analyzed to determine the necessary modifications and develop a plan for their implementation.

RESEARCH DESIGN

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING METHODS

In order to answer the first research question, the study can conduct a purposeful sample of tourism and hospitality graduates, employers, and other industry experts, such as career counselors, industry associations, and government officials. The sample size can be determined by data saturation, which occurs when the researcher collects data until no new themes or perspectives emerge. For the second research question, the researcher may undertake a purposive sample of students, faculty, and industry practitioners participating in informal learning activities at the bachelor's level tourism program at Hanoi University. To provide a comprehensive comprehension of the factors that influence the efficacy of informal learning, the sample may include both successful and unsuccessful cases. The researcher can use snowball sampling to recruit participants for the third research question, beginning with faculty members and then inviting students and recruiters who are familiar with the training courses and methods at Hanoi University.

QUESTION DEVELOPMENT AND INTERVIEW GUIDE

For the first research question, the interview inquiries can be open-ended and focused on eliciting the participants' experiences and perspectives regarding employability in the tourism and hospitality industries. For the second research question, interview queries can explore the effective strategies for enhancing informal learning as well as the factors that facilitate or impede its implementation. For the third research question, interview questions can explore the challenges and opportunities for modifying the training courses and methods at Hanoi University to accommodate the diverse demands of recruiters and assist tourism students in developing adaptive skills. In addition to the interview questions, which consist of main questions and probing questions, the researcher will develop analytic memos to make reference when performing data analysis and writing up the thesis.

Data Coding and Analysis:

The data can be thematically analyzed to determine the competencies required for employability in the industry and to construct a framework that takes into account both professional and personal competencies; the effective strategies for enhancing informal learning and the factors that facilitate or impede its implementation; the necessary modifications to the training courses and methods at Hanoi University and to develop a plan for implementing them.

To organize and identify themes in the study's data, qualitative data analysis software such as NVivo can be utilized. The themes can then be synthesized to de-

velop a comprehensive framework for employability, recommendations for enhancing the effectiveness of informal learning activities in the bachelor's program in tourism, and an action plan.

Observational strategies in the case study and action research methods:

Observational strategies can be used to collect data about the informal learning activities in the bachelor's program in tourism at Hanoi University and how the tourism industry and the university collaborate to improve their efficacy. Among the observational methods that can be employed are:

- Structured observation: The researcher can construct a list of pre-defined behaviors or events to observe during informal learning activities.
- Unstructured observation: The researcher can observe informal learning activities without a predetermined checklist and record any intriguing or pertinent observations.
- Participant observation: The researcher can participate in informal learning activities as a group member and observe the activities from an insider's vantage point.
- Non-participant observation: the researcher can observe informal learning activities without participating in them.

During the observational phase, comprehensive notes should be taken about what is being observed, including the behaviors and interactions of the participants, the physical environment, and any other contextual factors. Then, these notes can be used to supplement the interview and document analysis data in order to paint a more complete picture of the investigated phenomenon.

Observations can be used as a strategy in this action research method to collect data on how training courses and methods are conducted and the challenges participants face when adjusting to the workplace. To obtain a comprehensive understanding of the participants' experiences, observations can be conducted in various settings, including classrooms, training workshops, and industry workplaces.

The study may use techniques such as note-taking, recording, and video observation to conduct observations. The researcher takes notes of his or her observations during training sessions or in the workplace. The recording process involves the use of audio or video recording devices to capture the interactions and experiences of the participants. Video surveillance entails the recording of the behaviors and interactions of the participants, which can then be analyzed to identify patterns and themes.

During observations, the researcher can record the participants' behaviors, reactions, and interactions, as well as the surrounding environment in which they oc-

cur. The observations can be used to determine the obstacles that participants encounter in adjusting to the workplace and the necessary modifications to the training courses and methods.

Document analysis strategies in the case study method:

In this case study, document analysis can be used in conjunction with interviews and observations to collect data.

The documents that can be analyzed include course syllabi, program manuals, policies, and procedures related to the bachelor's degree program in tourism at Hanoi University, as well as reports, manuals, and training materials from the tourism industry.

To analyze the documents, the researcher may employ various strategies and methods, such as content analysis, discourse analysis, and critical discourse analysis. The purpose of content analysis is to identify patterns, themes, and categories in a text through systematic examination. Discourse analysis is concerned with how language constructs meaning and power relations. Critical discourse analysis adopts a more critical stance and concentrates on the power relations embedded in language and how they affect social structures and practices.

The analysis of the documents can shed light on the informal learning activities and strategies used in the bachelor's degree program in tourism at Hanoi University and in the industry, as well as the policies and procedures associated with them. The results of the document analysis can be combined with the information gathered through interviews and observations to achieve a thorough comprehension of the research question.

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